

Enrichment of Au-rich rims of disseminated pyrite in hydrothermal systems

Jia-Nan Fu ^{a,b}, Kun-Feng Qiu ^{a,*}, Xin Liu ^c, Zi-Yue Gao ^a, Richard Wirth ^b, Hao-Cheng Yu ^a, Franco Pirajno ^{a,d}, Lingli Zhou ^e, Jia-Yi Wang ^a, Jun Deng ^a

^a Frontiers Science Center for Deep-time Digital Earth, State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources, School of Earth Sciences and Resources, China University of Geosciences, Beijing 100083, China

^b GFZ Potsdam, Section 3.5 Interface Geochemistry, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

^c School of Material Sciences and Technology, China University of Geosciences, Beijing 100083, China

^d The University of Western Australia, 35 Stirling Hwy, Crawley, WA, 6009, Australia

^e Department of Earth Sciences, VU Amsterdam, De Boelelaan 1105, 1081 HV Amsterdam, Netherlands

* Corresponding author:

Kun-Feng Qiu kunfengqiu@qq.com

Professor, China University of Geosciences, Beijing

No. 29 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, 10083, P.R. China

Tel.: +86-10-82321383

Supplementary Figure 1. Activity of $\lg f(S_2)$ and temperature (T) projection of the stability field of arsenopyrite

Supplementary Figure 2. Representative time-resolved laser ablation depth profiles of various pyrite types showing variation in trace element concentrations. Insets show reflected-light photomicrographs of pyrites acquired with plane-polarized light with LA-ICP-MS spot. See text for discussion.

Supplementary Figure 3. (a) Crystal structure of pure pyrite ($2 \times 2 \times 2$ supercell); (b) substitution site. Brown ball: iron; Yellow ball: sulfur

Table S1. Trace Element Concentrations (in ppm) for Each Pyrite Type from the Liba Deposit.

Sample	Pyrite types	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Se	Ag	Sb	Te	W	Au	Pb	Bi	Ti
LB-1-1	Py _{core}	0.55	281.04	49.92	6.85	bd1	2499.76	4.22	1.2	8.17	2.52	0.04	0.4	10.1	0.16	3.47
LB-1-6-1	Py _{core}	28.51	6.28	53.34	33.5	1.01	3602.51	4.27	1.62	21.31	0.99	0.07	2.8	20.3	0.26	17.76
LB-1-2	Py _{core}	3.51	21.53	181.08	3.35	1.34	145.42	6.91	0.77	15.07	0.3	0.5	0.07	23.48	0.4	630.61
LB-1-3	Py _{core}	1.7	15.25	107.07	22.67	1.01	9017.88	9.29	0.77	13.69	1.03	0.24	0.41	8.43	0.43	132.66
LB-1-4	Py _{core}	0.55	92.59	22.55	5.62	2.87	457.45	5.31	1.34	8.16	0.96	bd1	1.02	15.07	0.5	4.73
LB-1-6-2	Py _{core}	335.07	53.06	291.31	24.54	5.1	6908.4	3.45	2.19	23.59	1.31	0.19	1.36	51.31	0.53	19.28
LB-1-1-1	Py _{core}	119.81	87.27	96.52	2.74	5.26	1658.53	7.58	0.77	6.58	0.3	0.04	0.02	8.87	0.55	141.19
LB-1-1-2	Py _{core}	25.3	50.97	1035.06	119.78	1.01	215.99	3.45	1.14	30.43	0.33	0.15	0.17	15.42	0.77	2.95
LB-1-6-3	Py _{core}	3.4	25.26	173.68	12.94	1.01	672.26	3.45	0.77	22.6	0.82	0.09	0.02	90.13	0.87	9.47
LB-1-5	Py _{core}	0.55	82.28	54.99	2.89	1.01	1654.33	3.45	1.02	19.05	1.46	bd1	0.17	42.4	1.51	3.45
LB-1-1-3	Py _{core}	5.99	348.87	397.19	6.9	1.01	572.74	3.69	0.77	49.14	2.26	0.15	0.36	83.63	4.53	7.17
LB-1-6	Py _{core}	bd1	0.55	1.15	0.72	1.01	1104.29	3.45	0.77	1.82	0.3	0.04	0.02	2.8	0.02	3.93
LB-1-7	Py _{core}	0.92	0.3	3.26	1.07	1.01	1101.02	3.45	0.77	6.35	0.47	0.04	0.02	4.14	0.02	5.62
LB-1-8	Py _{core}	0.55	50.59	11.5	0.96	1.52	2255.89	3.45	0.77	7.09	0.81	0.04	0.11	5.94	0.04	5.52
LB-1-9	Py _{core}	0.55	35.5	8.59	1.24	1.2	409.36	3.45	bd1	2.93	0.3	bd1	0.02	6.06	0.25	3.36
LB-1-10	Py _{core}	0.55	80.27	43.56	2.78	1.01	1951.91	bd1	0.77	5.62	2.05	0.04	0.02	21.13	0.45	3.68
LB-1-1-4	Py _{core}	13.55	97.96	350.88	8.29	1.7	612.9	3.45	0.77	47.81	1.38	0.04	0.17	69.48	7.25	25.54
LB-1-11	Py _{pore}	13.5	15.54	105.36	23.42	1.01	6244.04	3.45	0.85	26.66	1.83	bd1	0.67	40.34	0.16	1.93
LB-1-12	Py _{pore}	36.89	52.79	241.91	58.18	1.14	8953.1	8.4	2.02	91.09	1.65	0.22	1.97	143.73	0.3	60.82
LB-1-13	Py _{pore}	19.94	78.93	569.28	35.51	1.01	4388.7	6.19	0.85	39.72	0.48	0.04	0.85	89.69	0.33	2.72
LB-2-1	Py _{pore}	1.9	53.94	272.66	94.88	1.01	11952.03	bd1	1.65	59.2	0.32	1.38	0.62	24.63	0.44	333
LB-1-14	Py _{pore}	53.13	21.99	124.97	3.03	1.52	748.86	3.45	0.77	11.65	0.3	bd1	0.03	40.16	0.53	6.78
LB-1-6-4	Py _{pore}	23.98	64.53	464.84	52.74	1.01	8432.78	11.49	1.41	50.66	2.24	0.07	2.37	114.41	0.65	7.03
LB-1-5-1	Py _{pore}	83.99	48.88	440.03	67.56	5.13	14219.03	11.24	6.45	70.55	4.72	2.34	2.01	111.95	0.66	1380.94
LB-1-5-2	Py _{pore}	2.73	24.44	229.69	173.13	1.01	19491.31	6.49	2.91	119.1	4.61	1.4	0.6	124.32	0.67	524.24
LB-1-15	Py _{pore}	611.46	91.66	490.25	67.7	2.85	46851.67	10.35	3.46	138.8	51.71	0.31	5.13	262.2	0.67	8.42
LB-1-16	Py _{pore}	9.25	68.05	221.27	39.79	3.57	6689.76	7.78	3.98	97.59	2.77	0.29	1.28	147.4	0.85	63.4
LB-1-17	Py _{pore}	16.66	313.34	2093.2	24.46	1.01	5442.21	3.45	1.13	15.91	2.03	0.26	1.47	45.51	0.86	3.63
LB-1-18	Py _{pore}	1.62	16.23	80.31	8.32	1.01	1847.39	3.45	0.77	33.81	0.3	0.04	0.07	85.89	0.87	65.44
LB-1-19	Py _{pore}	598.29	57.63	387.83	62.36	4.72	9905.67	4.14	2.09	55.2	3.56	0.19	2.06	98.84	0.87	40.49
LB-1-20	Py _{pore}	11.53	33.12	252.05	168.26	6.44	26846.4	3.45	2.19	77.97	2.16	9.73	0.57	80.86	0.94	3758.44

LB-1-5-3	Py _{pore}	74.64	50.02	462.35	186.16	5.73	19793.09	6.91	3.56	152.99	6.76	3.62	2.82	326.58	1	1862.46
LB-2-2	Py _{pore}	5.81	25.26	126.06	43.74	1.01	7054.76	3.45	3.64	117.89	1.04	1.46	0.58	107.99	1.1	156.53
LB-2-3	Py _{pore}	bd1	286.76	203.11	37.39	1.4	1978.28	6.6	2.65	34.96	1	0.04	0.38	23.15	1.42	10.8
LB-2-4	Py _{pore}	0.55	230.39	140.25	6.7	1.01	1133.22	3.75	0.77	31.46	2.09	0.11	0.08	67.46	1.43	65.83
LB-2-5	Py _{pore}	13.59	24.85	172.28	67.49	1.01	9156.44	3.45	8.32	126.89	2.16	1.88	0.58	72.81	1.78	197.99
LB-2-6	Py _{pore}	21.7	28.13	198.31	22.82	1.01	4881.74	3.45	5.94	116.22	1.74	1.38	1.66	74.18	3.33	125.3
LB-2-7	Py _{pore}	5.24	4.79	82.83	38.99	1.01	7149.39	3.45	5.57	340.98	2.05	3.46	1.07	372.62	4.12	448.94
LB-1-1-5	Py _{pore}	0.88	423.2	822.71	64.82	1.58	5990.21	3.45	3.38	168.84	6.87	0.1	1.27	438.65	4.17	22.84
LB-2-7	Py _{pore}	413.61	271.21	1274.08	29.41	28.27	853.04	9.14	5.83	76.49	3.7	0.05	0.43	46.75	4.87	490.88
LB-2-8	Py _{pore}	150.12	726.41	1297.34	13.35	2.05	760.33	9.22	4.75	67.2	4.66	0.45	1.01	69.56	5.84	33.6
LB-2-9	Py _{pore}	44.59	630.16	968.22	96.62	15.72	7863.13	5.74	5.22	149.23	12.09	0.04	2.08	143.44	6.46	27.1
LB-1-1-6	Py _{pore}	25.9	71.58	455.53	156.78	1.01	36934.18	11.08	8.77	632.66	18.66	0.22	4.1	1421.44	7.05	115.93
LB-2-10	Py _{mantle}	bd1	32.9	346.84	45.05	1.11	4296.7	9.61	bd1	2.82	0.3	0.07	8.8	4.65	0.02	9.52
LB-2-11	Py _{mantle}	0.55	9.61	221.46	81.59	1.01	4122.17	13	0.77	5.91	bd1	0.06	12.77	5.08	0.06	2.91
LB-2-12	Py _{mantle}	125.89	104.62	469.12	54.49	11.7	3904.88	5.85	0.77	10.39	0.67	2.54	4.56	19.37	0.09	250.91
LB-2-13	Py _{mantle}	10.73	171.01	271.58	63.66	1.93	6536.61	8.14	0.97	13.12	0.49	0.42	5	9.74	0.1	45.59
LB-1-21	Py _{mantle}	12.06	41.76	396.18	19.42	1.89	3786.14	8.08	bd1	3.12	0.3	0.45	2.95	12.2	0.12	307.22
LB-1-22	Py _{mantle}	2.72	46.17	146.53	85.02	1.01	2366.29	4.41	1.3	10.4	0.3	3.42	7.69	14.17	0.15	166.86
LB-1-23	Py _{mantle}	bd1	16.8	156.59	34.86	1.01	12138.29	7.08	2.47	39.88	3.48	0.14	1.31	66.84	0.16	29.44
LB-1-24	Py _{mantle}	0.57	10.49	94.22	13.29	1.32	10660.15	3.45	2.59	67.49	2.33	0.29	0.28	82.29	0.17	144.1
LB-1-25	Py _{mantle}	938	34.14	218.3	73.66	5.53	5695.16	7.65	0.77	14.09	0.93	0.04	11.33	19.87	0.18	4.82
LB-1-6-4	Py _{mantle}	0.89	12.01	55.15	96.41	1.01	7259.2	12.62	3.34	23.2	1.23	0.04	19.87	17.59	0.24	4.25
LB-1-6-5	Py _{mantle}	21.86	15.29	109.3	97.56	2.01	9244.79	4.35	4.34	33.83	2.64	bd1	9.85	42.63	0.42	3
LB-1-1-6	Py _{mantle}	15.57	26.43	205.97	108.24	1.89	20134.54	6.03	2.98	77.86	7.31	0.05	2.47	74.81	0.43	13.63
LB-1-1-7	Py _{mantle}	38.41	30.57	247.82	107.6	2.52	19277.39	4.45	2.21	69.14	2.41	0.22	0.95	114.05	0.47	72.5
LB-1-1-8	Py _{mantle}	6.4	21.92	175.27	119.95	1.79	21697.99	9	5.16	100.76	5.79	1.2	1.22	69.62	0.47	298.92
LB-2-13	Py _{mantle}	5.37	24.15	247.81	57.49	2.78	8640.56	5.55	9.76	104.14	3.8	26.43	3.31	51.83	0.48	4604.2
LB-2-14	Py _{mantle}	3.61	9.37	96.96	236.67	1.01	33780.3	15.28	9.75	70.76	1.77	0.66	13.29	33.41	0.52	26.28
LB-2-15	Py _{mantle}	0.91	7.1	88.76	204.15	1.01	19519.7	6.42	4.89	35.24	9.29	0.04	16.61	40.27	0.56	4.68
LB-1-1-8	Py _{mantle}	139.79	59.41	371.12	62.64	8.5	18862.54	bd1	3.35	82.73	12.27	0.26	9.12	133.03	0.58	32.18
LB-1-1-9	Py _{mantle}	2.2	18.43	178.54	145.02	1.23	18375.16	13.13	4.52	39.17	4.78	0.33	8.41	47.12	0.58	8.69
LB-1-1-10	Py _{mantle}	36.2	36.42	227.65	155.26	5.36	13873.92	6.15	3.61	31.79	8.47	0.07	17.31	55.03	0.62	6.02
LB-1-1-11	Py _{mantle}	39.23	37.77	285.97	175.13	4.41	17374.51	7.88	3.56	82.63	3.4	0.69	16.53	122.4	0.64	241.92

LB-1-1-12	Py _{mantle}	3.9	26.39	226.46	171.53	6.5	20491.72	12	1.67	50.36	4.44	0.04	5.48	48.57	0.69	4.06
LB-1-1-13	Py _{mantle}	7.04	62.5	385.5	41.97	2.63	10277.7	3.45	1.7	55.71	1.45	2.66	1.65	86.51	0.69	917.36
LB-1-1-14	Py _{mantle}	4.39	201.13	774.72	115.08	3.32	8761.72	bd1	2.44	31.49	2.34	0.1	7.05	47.14	0.83	5.81
LB-1-1-15	Py _{mantle}	6.04	35.65	228.66	133.35	1.01	26250.48	9.67	3.32	53.37	25.2	0.13	13.27	49.83	1.21	21.9
LB-1-1-16	Py _{mantle}	1.35	12.42	42.24	46.05	1.5	19453.24	7.86	0.77	87.86	0.36	0.04	3.11	282.69	3.14	5.4
LB-1-26	Py _{light rim}	0.55	9.68	242.94	705.73	1.14	20047.78	15.08	0.89	4.55	0.82	bd1	105.39	2.04	0.04	4.04
LB-2-16	Py _{light rim}	0.55	55.54	393.29	673.71	bd1	27396.49	22.33	0.77	7.2	3.18	1.27	67.68	6.59	0.04	360.24
LB-2-17	Py _{light rim}	32.21	67.55	196.66	253.42	3.4	14305.5	9.53	0.77	4.11	0.6	0.19	39.38	5.51	0.04	40.01
LB-2-18	Py _{light rim}	1.54	42.87	232.03	237.12	1.97	17791.99	10.7	2.32	21.71	2.21	6.47	32.18	21.52	0.1	2060.1
LB-1-1-17	Py _{light rim}	0.69	8.12	100.2	324.54	2.06	26575.83	11.71	4.45	54.12	3.68	0.42	33.7	36.06	0.22	327.51
LB-1-27	Py _{light rim}	1.34	4.81	62.64	148.07	2.56	26973.54	13.44	0.77	15.21	12.27	0.05	27.41	18.98	0.37	4.44
LB-1-6-4	Py _{light rim}	0.95	13.93	131.11	192.63	4.21	26699.14	7.89	4.52	43.79	6.82	0.04	27.9	37.9	0.57	8.44
LB-1-6-5	Py _{light rim}	0.91	1.71	38.6	382.74	1.01	29385.4	15.39	10.24	58.81	6.09	0.04	66.83	48.89	0.61	3.72
LB-1-27	Py _{light rim}	17.66	66.97	485.12	468.32	3.65	54002.03	20.82	3.43	46.28	67.34	0.6	110.38	33.99	0.97	61.2
LB-1-28	Py _{light rim}	4.16	23.22	393.1	490.19	1.01	60529.61	17.52	21.62	110.52	21.99	0.04	45.01	41.97	0.97	3.69
LB-1-5-4	Py _{light rim}	36.65	54.26	375.63	403.89	10.86	28624.09	18.88	7.95	49.43	12.94	0.1	91.8	109.86	1.42	98.45
LB-1-28	Py _{light rim}	3.39	2.88	171.84	517.7	1.52	27528.15	21.78	90.9	188.21	6.1	bd1	285.23	153.75	1.44	4.28
LB-1-29	Py _{light rim}	144.75	318.68	737.95	379.28	42.08	24900.68	14.18	4.06	64.47	9	0.18	76.33	86.46	1.77	35.58
LB-1-6-5	Py _{dark rim}	1.26	10.57	91.87	0.84	1.01	1761.72	16.68	bd1	0.64	bd1	bd1	0.09	1.25	bd1	5.61
LB-2-18	Py _{dark rim}	0.55	87.13	513.21	bd1	1.01	2762.14	3.45	0.77	1.02	0.3	0.05	0.02	1.18	0.02	5.89
LB-2-19	Py _{dark rim}	0.64	14.75	333.36	0.26	1.96	1786.67	9.11	0.77	5.08	0.3	0.04	0.04	3.26	0.02	3.29
LB-1-30	Py _{dark rim}	0.55	121.03	329.96	0.25	1.32	1784.55	10.15	0.77	0.86	0.3	0.07	0.06	1.19	0.02	5.3

Table S2: chemical compositions of arsenopyrite at the Liba gold deposit

Spot No.	Elements (wt %)															Chemical Formula
	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	S	Pb	Au	Ag	Te	Sb	Bi	Se	As	Total	
LB-2-1	34.65	0.14	0.16	0.00	0.00	21.23	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.15	43.08	99.61	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.07}
LB-2-2	34.74	0.18	0.46	0.00	0.01	21.04	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.05	42.81	99.37	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.06}
LB-2-3	34.15	0.19	0.26	0.00	0.00	20.52	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.03	44.97	100.17	FeAs _{0.98} S _{1.05}
LB-2-4	35.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.44	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	46.44	101.09	FeAs _{0.99} S _{0.97}
LB-2-5	35.62	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.00	20.65	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.04	43.76	100.37	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.01}
LB-2-6	35.08	0.12	0.16	0.00	0.00	20.94	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06	42.60	99.02	FeAs _{0.91} S _{1.04}
LB-1-7	35.48	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	20.87	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.04	45.01	101.45	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.03}
LB-1-8	34.72	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	21.92	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.18	43.21	100.15	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.10}
LB-1-10	35.29	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.01	20.81	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	43.87	100.17	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.03}
LB-1-11	33.26	1.23	0.43	0.01	0.00	19.71	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	44.41	99.25	FeAs _{1.00} S _{1.04}
LB-1-12	33.15	1.30	0.37	0.00	0.00	19.25	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.09	46.33	100.55	FeAs _{1.04} S _{1.02}
LB-1-13	32.13	2.55	0.47	0.01	0.01	18.98	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	45.91	100.14	FeAs _{1.07} S _{1.03}
LB-1-14	33.95	0.77	0.26	0.00	0.00	19.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	45.22	100.05	FeAs _{0.99} S _{1.02}
LB-1-15	35.05	0.05	0.11	0.00	0.01	20.28	0.02	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13	43.77	99.49	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.01}
LB-1-16	35.27	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.00	20.69	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.10	44.32	100.61	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.03}
LB-1-17	35.73	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.00	20.57	0.19	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.11	44.87	101.57	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.01}
LB-1-18	34.73	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.00	20.07	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.11	45.23	100.45	FeAs _{0.97} S _{1.01}
LB-1-19	35.61	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	20.64	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.01	44.33	100.89	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.01}
LB-1-20	35.40	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.00	20.62	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.12	43.87	100.22	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.02}
LB-1-21	35.53	0.05	0.07	0.00	0.00	21.26	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.10	43.69	100.76	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.05}
LB-1-22	35.07	0.09	0.19	0.02	0.00	21.83	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.06	43.40	100.74	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.09}
LB-1-23	34.77	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.00	20.37	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.08	45.10	100.49	FeAs _{0.97} S _{1.03}
LB-1-24	35.09	0.24	0.21	0.00	0.00	20.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.08	43.95	100.34	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.03}
LB-1-25	34.71	0.05	0.10	0.00	0.00	20.67	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.07	44.17	99.93	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.04}

LB-1-26	35.29	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.00	20.21	0.02	0.08	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.11	44.39	100.22	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.00}
LB-1-27	34.71	0.05	0.10	0.04	0.00	20.79	0.11	0.07	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.07	43.31	99.36	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.05}
LB-1-28	35.19	0.10	0.00	0.04	0.00	19.95	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.13	46.01	101.48	FeAs _{0.98} S _{0.99}
LB-1-29	34.80	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.05	20.97	0.07	0.03	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.10	44.35	100.45	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.05}
LB-1-30	35.69	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.00	20.37	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	45.40	101.64	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.00}
LB-1-31	35.16	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.04	20.82	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	44.04	100.28	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.04}
LB-1-32	35.28	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.00	21.08	0.07	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.11	43.52	100.56	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.05}
LB-1-33	34.49	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.02	20.75	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.04	44.22	99.69	FeAs _{0.96} S _{1.05}
LB-1-34	34.75	0.07	0.01	0.00	0.00	20.03	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.14	44.79	99.90	FeAs _{0.96} S _{1.01}
LB-1-35	34.72	0.28	0.39	0.06	0.00	20.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.05	43.59	99.92	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.05}
LB-1-36	35.53	0.04	0.00	0.03	0.00	20.94	0.07	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.09	43.92	100.82	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.03}
LB-1-37	34.99	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	20.39	0.00	0.11	0.01	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.05	44.50	100.25	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.02}
LB-1-38	35.10	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	20.02	0.09	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.08	45.42	100.86	FeAs _{0.97} S _{1.00}
LB-1-39	34.80	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.01	20.31	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.14	43.98	99.47	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.02}
LB-1-40	35.22	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	20.78	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.08	44.46	100.66	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.03}
LB-1-41	35.26	0.05	0.00	0.02	0.00	20.85	0.12	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.11	43.94	100.48	FeAs _{0.93} S _{1.03}
LB-1-42	35.01	0.02	0.00	0.09	0.04	20.93	0.10	0.08	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.09	44.25	100.69	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.05}
LB-1-43	34.95	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.03	20.28	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.12	44.96	100.49	FeAs _{0.96} S _{1.02}
LB-1-44	35.27	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.55	0.13	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	44.99	101.16	FeAs _{0.95} S _{1.02}
LB-1-46	35.01	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.00	20.47	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.11	44.95	100.75	FeAs _{0.96} S _{1.02}
LB-3-1	35.28	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.01	21.99	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.23	43.41	101.04	FeAs _{0.92} S _{1.09}
LB-3-2	35.85	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	22.12	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.18	42.70	101.00	FeAs _{0.89} S _{1.08}
LB-3-3	35.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	21.24	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.06	44.33	101.08	FeAs _{0.94} S _{1.05}

First-principles calculations method

The spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed using the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP.6.4.2) (Kresse and Furthmuller 1996) along with the projector augmented wave (PAW) method (Kresse and Joubert 1999). Standard PAW pseudopotentials (Fe: d^7s^1 , S: s^2p^4 , Au: s^1d^{10} , Cu: $d^{10}p^1$ and As: s^2p^3) were used. The generalized gradient approximation (GGA) formulation by Perdew, Burke, and Enzerhoff (PBE) functional (Perdew et al. 1996) was used to describe the exchange-correlation interaction among electrons. The convergence of the cutoff and k-point meshes are tested for primitive pyrite, and the energy of 600 eV was used as a cutoff value for the plane wave basis and a 6×6×6 Monkhorst-Pack k-mesh was used during structural relaxation. Total energies were converged at 10^{-6} eV. The simplified Hubbard U correction (GGA+ U) method (Dudarev et al. 1998) was employed to describe the 3d electrons of Fe element. The parameter $U-J=1.6$ eV was employed, and the feasibility of such a parameter was confirmed by previous studies on pyritic systems (Xian et al. 2021; He et al. 2023). The calculated lattice constant of 5.426 is in well agreement with both the experimental data and previous calculations. All the structures employed in this study were relaxed until forces became smaller than 0.001 eV/Å. The configuration files of reference materials were downloaded from the American Mineralogist Crystal Structure Database website. Structure relaxation of these configurations was modeled by the unit cells. The pyrites with Au, As, Cu substitution were modeled by 2×2×2 supercells with 96 atoms. A 3×3×3 Monkhorst-Pack k-mesh was used for supercell (including doping model) structural relaxation and during the final static calculation for accurate total energies. Previous studies report that Au and Cu mainly occupy the Fe site and As mainly occupy the S site in the pyrite lattice and these kind of incorporation of Au are used to study substitution model in the calculation (Fu et al., 2024; He et al., 2023; Voute et al., 2019).

The incorporation energies were calculated and it refers to the energies required for an As (Au or Cu) atom to incorporate into the crystal. Here, incorporation energies in these models were calculated through the equation:

$$E_{incorporation} = E_{product}^{total} + E_{atom}^{sub} - E_{reactant}^{total} - E_{As (Cu or Au)}$$

$E_{product}^{total}$ and $E_{reactant}^{total}$ are the total energies of those doping pyrites and matrix pyrites, respectively. E_{atom}^{sub} is defined as the calculated energies of the substituted matrix atom (Fe or S) and $E_{As (Cu or Au)}$ is defined as the calculated energies of As, Cu or Au atom.

- Benbattouche, N., Saunders, G.A., Lambson, E.F., Honle, W., 1989. The dependences of the elastic stiffness moduli and the Poisson ratio of natural iron pyrites FeS₂ upon pressure and temperature. *Journal of Physics D. Appl. Phys.* 22, 670–675.
- Kresse, G., Furthmüller, J., 1996. Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set. *Comp Mater Sci.* 6, 15–50.
- Kresse, G., and Joubert, D., 1999. From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method. *Phys. Rev. B.* 59, 1758–1775.
- Perdew, J.P., Burke, K., Ernzerhof, M., 1996. Generalized gradient approximation made simple. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 77, 3865–3868.
- Dudarev, S.L., Botton, G.A., Savrasov, S.Y., Humphreys, C.J., Sutton, A.P., 1998. Electron-energy-loss spectra and the structural stability of nickel oxide: An LSDA+U study. *Phys. Rev. B.* 57, 1505–1509.
- Jain, A., Ong, S.P., Hautier, G., Chen, W., Richards, W.D., Dacek, S., Cholia, S., Gunter, D., Skinner, D., Ceder, G., Persson, K.A., 2013. Commentary: The Materials Project: A materials genome approach to accelerating materials innovation. *APL Mater*, 1, 011002 011002.
- Rettig S J, Trotter J., 1987. Refinement of the structure of orthorhombic sulfur, α -S₈. *Acta Crystallogr C.* 43(12): 2260-2262.
- Schiferl D, Barrett C S., 1969. The crystal structure of arsenic at 4.2, 78 and 299 K. *J Appl Crystallogr.* 2(1): 30-36.
- Suh, I.K., Ohta, H., Waseda, Y., 1988. High-temperature thermal expansion of six metallic elements measured by dilatation method and X-ray diffraction. *J. Mater.* 23, 757–760.
- Wilburn, D.R., Bassett, W.A., 1978. Hydrostatic compression of iron and related compounds; an overview. *Am. Mineral.* 63, 591–596.
- Xian, H., Wu, X., Zhu, J., Du, R., Wei, J., Zhu, R., He, H., 2021. Environmental sulfur-controlled surface properties of pyrite: a first principles PBE+U study. *Phys. Chem. Miner.* 48, 20.